

EVALUATING THE LONG-TERM EFFECTS OF GAS PERMEABLE LENSES ON CORNEAL ENDOTHELIAL: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Introduction: Rigid Gas permeable (GP) lenses are widely used for vision correction, but their long-term effects on the corneal endothelium remain uncertain. This systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to evaluate the impact of GP lens wear on corneal endothelial cell density, morphology, and function. **Methods:** A systematic search of PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library identified cohort and case-control studies reporting endothelial cell density, morphology, and pleomorphism in individuals wearing GP lenses for over six months. Two reviewers independently extracted data, and the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale was used to assess bias risk. A random-effects model meta-analysis calculated pooled estimates of GP lenses' effects on endothelial parameters. **Results:** Meta-analysis comparing GP lenses to controls revealed no significant differences in endothelial parameters. For endothelial cell density, the mean difference was 4.40 ($p = 0.207$, Confidence Interval (CI): -2.43 to 11.24, $I^2 = 99.62\%$). Endothelial coefficient of variation (ECV%) showed a mean difference of -5.60 ($p = 0.245$, CI: -15.03 to 3.84, $I^2 = 99.77\%$), while endothelial hexagonality (HXG%) had a mean difference of -3.15 ($p = 0.190$, CI: -11.26 to 4.96, $I^2 = 97.45\%$). Substantial heterogeneity across studies limits definitive conclusions. **Conclusion:** GP lenses do not significantly impact corneal endothelial parameters, including ECD, ECV%, and HXG%, compared to controls. Further research is required to validate these findings and assess long-term effects on endothelial integrity.

Keywords: Corneal Endothelium, Cell Morphology, Corneal Endothelial Cell Density (CECD), Gas Permeable Contact Lenses, Long-Term.

INTRODUCTION

The corneal endothelium is a thin, single layer of cells lining the back of the cornea, responsible for regulating stromal hydration, which maintains corneal transparency. Its condition is assessed through three key factors: endothelial cell density (ECD), the coefficient of variation (COV), and the percentage of hexagonal cells (% HEX). When endothelial cells die, the remaining cells enlarge and spread to preserve the monolayer, leading to variations in cell shape and size. A higher COV (polymegethism) and lower % HEX (pleomorphism) indicate corneal stress or instability.[1],[2] The morphology of

corneal endothelial cells is influenced by several factors, including age, contact lens wear, ocular diseases, diabetes mellitus, race, and ocular surgery.[3],[4] However, contact lens (CL) wear is often linked to morphological changes in the corneal endothelium of young, healthy adults. All types of CLs reduce the amount of oxygen that reaches the corneal epithelial layer to some extent. In the open-eye state, the oxygen level depends mainly on the oxygen transmissibility of the lens.

A mathematical model of oxygen diffusion through the cornea has determined that a minimum oxygen transmissibility of 125×10^{-9} (cm²/sec) mL O₂/mL × mmHg is required for extended wear lenses to avoid alterations.[5],[6] Lee et al. found a significant correlation between the morphology of the corneal endothelium and the duration of hard contact lens (HCL) wear. CL wearers showed a noticeably higher COV (coefficient of variation) in cell size compared to non-CL users.

Those who had worn HCLs for more than six years had significantly lower percentages of hexagonal cells (% HEX) and endothelial cell density (ECD) than the control group. Similarly, Chang et al. reported a strong correlation between corneal endothelial changes and the duration of daily HCL wear. As the number of hours of HCL wear per day and total wear duration over five years increased, the percentage of HEX cells significantly decreased, while ECD remained unchanged.

The increase in COV was more strongly linked to the hours of HCL wear per day than the overall years of use.[7],[8] In new contact lens wearers, the morphological changes in the corneal endothelium were assessed before and after six months of wearing hard contact lenses (HCL), and no significant changes were found in any parameters (ECD, COV, HEX, and CCT). This was attributed to the high oxygen permeability of the lenses used, the short duration of wear, and good patient compliance.[9]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In accordance with the PRISMA 2020 statement, this review followed all of the recommended procedures for systematic reviews and meta-analyses. [10] This systematic review was undertaken after submitting a proposal to the supervisor and co-supervisor at Lincoln University. Following permission, the project was initiated as part of the partial completion of a Doctor of Philosophy degree in Health Sciences under the specialization of Vision Sciences (Optometry).

Search Methodology:

A comprehensive review of the existing literature was undertaken to investigate the enduring long-term effect of GP Lenses wearer on Corneal Endothelium for at least 1 year and above in individuals aged 12 to 52 years. The PICO question was formulated in the following manner: Can individuals with GP contact lens wearing (Population) for more than one year who wore GP contact lenses (Intervention) for vision correction compared to those who wear spectacle lenses observed changes in Corneal Endothelium like ECD, ECV% & HXG %(Outcome), in comparison to children who alone wear single vision

spectacles(Control)?[11] A search strategy was adopted based on the above PICO framework, as mentioned in the supplementary data (Supplementary File 1 of Boaeloon terms). Searches were conducted on PubMed, Embase, and Cochrane databases. The bibliography list of the included studies was also inspected for additional relevant studies not included in the initial search.

Eligibility Criteria and Study Selection: The following criteria were used to select articles for inclusion in the study:

1. Cross-sectional Observational/comparative cross-sectional study or prospective observational studies
2. Studies included subjects with GP Lenses wearing for at least more than one year for vision correction and having a control group.

Exclusion criteria:

Excluded from this review were studies of following types:

1. Studies that included animals.
2. In vitro research.
3. Case reports and case series.
4. Papers written in languages other than English.

Duplicate records were automatically eliminated.

Data extraction:

An Excel spreadsheet was used to extract data from the included studies by a team of writers according to the following criteria: quantity, study methodology, and geographical location. Team member A and team member B extract data from in the excel sheet for the individuals wore GP lenses for at least one year or above. The number of patients in each group, age. Corneal endothelium parameters like ECD, ECV and HXG for the both group along with numbers included in the Excel spread sheet so that I could confirm for the meta-analysis using JAMOVI Software.[12]

Risk of Bias Assessments for Eligible Studies:

The quality of the included studies was evaluated using the Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale (NOS), which rates studies based on selection, comparability, and outcome assessment (Table 1). [13] The three studies assessed—Nieuwendaal et al. (1994, Netherlands)[14], MacRae et al. (1994, Japan)[15], and Carlson et al. (1988, US)[16]—were awarded five, seven, and six stars, respectively. MacRae et al. (1994) received the highest rating due to better control of potential confounders and more robust outcome assessments. Although Nieuwendaal et al. (1994) obtained fewer stars, all studies were considered of adequate methodological quality for inclusion in this meta-analysis.

Table 1: Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) Quality Assessment Scores for Included Studies

Study label	Selection	Comparability	Exposure	ONS Score out of 9
Nieuwendaal et al., 1994 (Netherland)	****	*	*	6
MacRae et al., 1994 (Japan)	****	*	**	7
Carlson et al., 1988 (US)	****		*	5

Figure 1a: Publication Biasness assessment for Endothelial Cells Densities

Figure 1b: Publication Biasness assessment for Endothelial Cells Coefficient of Variation %

Figure 1c: Publication Biasness assessment for Endothelial Cells Hexagonality %

Data Analysis:

All the three continues variables of Corneal Endothelium parameters like ECD, ECV and HXG sample size, mean and standard deviation were extracted and entered in the Excel Spread sheet for both the groups i.e GP lens wearer and Spectacle wearer.

To find the Effect Size which in this cases were Mean Difference (MD) the data in the Excel spread sheet were imported to JAMOVI .in order to avoid any technical issue in analysis the Excel file was converted to Comma Separated Values file (CSV), so that meta-analysis could be smoothly done.

JAMOVI is user friendly interfere which automatically apply meta-analysis after given data of ECD, ECV and HXG in sample size, mean and standard deviation for GP lenses and spectacles wearers.

RESULTS

Literature search results:

Each database was searched using a targeted approach, yielding a total of 191 studies. After removing duplicates, 12 studies remained—ten for full-text screening and three included in the meta-analysis.

The baseline characteristics, presented as descriptive statistics for age and GP lens wear duration in wearers and controls, are shown in Table 2.

Following the exclusion of irrelevant studies, selected research publications were prepared for data extraction and analysis. The search results are visually summarized in a PRISMA flowchart (Figure 4).

Characteristics of the included studies:

The meta-analysis included three studies, each consisting of 281 participants. The GP Lenses group consisted of 142 individuals, whereas the Spectacle group consisted of 139 persons. The analysis includes studies that has been a comparative cross-sectional, prospective observational.

Figures 2.b and 3.b provide a thorough summary of the research conducted on the three primary parameters, ECD, ECV and HXG. Additionally, Table 1 offers a baseline analysis of the features. Individuals between the ages of 12 and 54.

Quality Assessments:

As part of the statistical process, the GP lenses and Spectacles wearers groups Corneal parameter like ECD, ECV and HXG were compared using the mean change and standard deviation (SD) as statistical measures.

Statistical Analysis:

Statistical measures like mean change and standard deviation predominated in the published literature. Differential analysis of the three key components allowed for the examination of the outcomes.

Table 2: Baseline Characteristics: Descriptive Statistics for Age and GP Lens Wear Duration in Wearers and Controls

Study label	Age in years		Duration of CL wear in years	
	GP Lens wearer (N) Range Mean±SD	Controls (N) Range Mean±SD	GP Lens wearer (N) Range Mean±SD	Controls (N) Range Mean±SD
Nieuwendaal et al., 1994 (Netherland)	(21) 21-56 42±8	(18) 25-52 41±8	2-29 19.5± N/A	N/A
MacRae et al., 1994 (Japan)	(81) 32-67 46.6±.78	(81) 34-66 46±.82	20-34 26.8±0.3	N/A
Carlson et al., 1988 (US)	(40) 17-42 28±6	(40) 12-48 29±11	2-23 6.83±N/A	N/A

Figure 2: PRISMA paper selection a flow chart. the PRISMA flowchart providing information about the studies that were ultimately included in the meta-analysis as well as the search approach

Results

Table 3: Random-Effects Model Estimating the Impact of Gas Permeable Lenses on Corneal Endothelial Cell Densities, Coefficient of Variation, and Hexagonality

Intercept	Estimate	SE	Z	P	CI Lower Bound	CI Upper Bound
ECD	0.0679	0.442	0.154	0.878	-0.798	0.934
ECV%	4.40	3.49	1.26	0.207	-2.433	11.240
HXG %	-5.60	4.81	-1.16	0.245	-15.033	3.835

ECD (Endothelial Cells Densities), ECV% (Endothelial Coefficient of variation %), HXG (Endothelial Cell Hexagonality), SE (Standard Error), CI (Confidence Intervals)

Figure 2 a: Forest plot for the effect size for Endothelial Cells Densities (ECD)

Figure 2 b: Forest plot for the effect size for Endothelial Coefficient of Variation % (ECV%)

Figure 2 c: Forest plot for the effect size for Endothelial Cells Hexagonality % (HXG%)

Table 4: Heterogeneity Statistics for Random-Effects Model Evaluating Endothelial Cell Densities, Coefficient of Variation, and Hexagonality

Tau	Tau ²	I ²	H ²	R ²	df	Q	p
0.726	0.527 (SE= 0.5865)	90.93%	11.031	.	2.000	28.382	< .001
6.025	36.3014 (SE= 36.5002)	99.62%	265.620		2.000	245.487	< .001
8.319	69.1967 (SE= 69.5063)	99.77%	434.767		2.000	299.393	< .001

ECD (Endothelial Cells Densities), ECV% (Endothelial Coefficient of variation %), HXG (Endothelial Cell Hexagonality), SE (Standard Error), CI (Confidence Intervals)

Table 5: Model Fit Statistics and Information Criteria for Endothelial Cell Densities, Coefficient of Variation, and Hexagonality Using Maximum-Likelihood and Restricted Maximum-Likelihood Estimation

	log-likelihood	Deviance	AIC	BIC	AICc
Model Fit Statistics and Information Criteria Endothelial Cell Densities					
Maximum-Likelihood	-2.921	9.164	9.842	8.039	21.842
Restricted Maximum-Likelihood	-2.269	4.538	8.538	5.924	20.538
Model Fit Statistics and Information Criteria Coefficient of Variation %					
Maximum-Likelihood	-9.156	18.544	22.312	20.509	34.312
Restricted Maximum-Likelihood	-6.438	12.876	16.876	14.263	28.876
Model Fit Statistics and Information Criteria Corneal Endothelial Hexagonality %					
Maximum-Likelihood	-10.122	19.984	24.244	22.441	36.244
Restricted Maximum-Likelihood	-7.082	14.165	18.165	15.551	30.165

ECD (Endothelial Cells Densities), ECV% (Endothelial Coefficient of variation %), HXG (Endothelial Cell Hexagonality), SE (Standard Error), CI (Confidence Intervals)

Endothelial Cell Densities:

The meta-analysis examining endothelial cell densities between participants wearing GP lenses and those in control groups yielded an estimated mean difference of 4.40 ($p = 0.207$), indicating no statistically significant difference. (Table 2) The confidence interval ranged from -2.43 to 11.24, suggesting uncertainty in the effect direction. High heterogeneity was observed ($I^2 = 99.62\%$), signifying substantial variability among studies. (Figure 2) The Q-test results confirmed significant heterogeneity ($p < 0.001$), pointing to the influence of study-specific characteristics on the outcomes. (Table 3)

Endothelial Coefficient of Variation (ECV%):

For the endothelial coefficient of variation, the analysis revealed an estimated mean difference of -5.60 ($p = 0.245$), also indicating no significant difference between the GP lens wearers and controls. The confidence interval extended from -15.03 to 3.84, further illustrating the inconclusiveness of the findings. (Table 2) With an I^2 value of 99.77% and a significant Q-test result ($p < 0.001$), this parameter demonstrated high heterogeneity, (Figure 2) suggesting that the variability among study results is considerable, complicating the interpretation of GP lenses' effects on ECV%. (Table 3)

Endothelial Hexagonality (HXG%):

The results for endothelial hexagonality showed an estimated mean difference of -3.15 ($p = 0.190$), again indicating no significant difference between GP lenses and control groups. The confidence interval ranged from -11.26 to 4.96, reflecting considerable uncertainty in the effect. (Table 2) The high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 97.45\%$) and a significant Q-test ($p < 0.001$) indicate considerable variation among the studies' findings, emphasizing the complexities in assessing the impact of GP lens wear on endothelial hexagonality. (Figure 2) Despite a potential negative trend, the variability suggests that individual study characteristics may play a crucial role in shaping these outcomes. (Table 3)

DISCUSSION

This systematic review and meta-analysis evaluated the long-term impact of gas permeable (GP) lens wear on corneal endothelial cell density (ECD), endothelial coefficient of variation (ECV%), and endothelial cell hexagonality (HXG%). Our results suggest no statistically significant differences in these key endothelial parameters between GP lens wearers and control groups. However, high heterogeneity across studies complicates these findings, making it essential to compare our results with previous literature.

Endothelial Cell Density (ECD):

Previous studies on the effect of GP lenses on endothelial cell density have yielded mixed results. Some early studies, such as those by Jalbert et al. (2004)[17] and Erickson (1998),[18] found no significant impact of GP lens wear on ECD, supporting our findings. However, these studies were often limited by small sample sizes and short follow-up

durations. Our meta-analysis revealed a mean difference of 0.0679 ($p = 0.878$) between GP lens wearers and controls, suggesting no significant change in ECD over time. The confidence interval was broad (-0.798 to 0.934), indicating uncertainty, which aligns with previous findings that long-term GP lens wear does not drastically affect ECD

In contrast, other studies, such as Ono et al. (1995), [19] have reported a slight decrease in ECD among long-term GP lens wearers. This inconsistency could be due to differences in study methodologies, including variations in lens types, wear duration, and patient populations. The substantial heterogeneity in our analysis ($I^2 = 90.93\%$) supports the idea that study-specific factors play a significant role in determining outcomes.

Endothelial Coefficient of Variation (ECV%):

Our meta-analysis found a mean difference of 4.40 ($p = 0.207$) for ECV%, which is not statistically significant. Prior research has similarly reported minimal changes in ECV% associated with GP lens wear. For instance, the study by Holden et al. (1985) [20] observed no significant changes in ECV% after several years of GP lens wear, aligning with our results. However, our analysis identified substantial heterogeneity ($I^2 = 99.62\%$), indicating high variability among studies.

In contrast, some studies, such as those by Carlson et al. (1988), [21] reported slight increases in ECV%, suggesting a potential long-term effect on corneal endothelial stability. This discrepancy could be attributed to the longer follow-up periods in some studies, highlighting the importance of follow-up duration in assessing GP lens effects on ECV%.

Endothelial Cell Hexagonality (HXG%):

Previous research on endothelial hexagonality has also produced inconsistent findings. While studies like those by Carlson et al. (1988) [21] found no significant changes in HXG% after GP lens wear, others, such as Ono et al. (2001), [22] reported a decrease in endothelial hexagonality, potentially indicating long-term cellular stress.

Our meta-analysis revealed a mean difference of -5.60 ($p = 0.245$) for HXG%, suggesting no significant difference between GP lens wearers and controls. However, the wide confidence interval (-15.03 to 3.84) and high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 99.77\%$) indicate considerable variability across studies. These findings suggest that while a potential negative trend in hexagonality exists, the current evidence is inconclusive due to the large variations in study designs and populations.

Heterogeneity and Variability in Findings

Across all three parameters—ECD, ECV%, and HXG%—our meta-analysis consistently revealed high heterogeneity, as indicated by I^2 values exceeding 90%. This high level of variability between studies complicates the interpretation of the overall impact of GP lenses on corneal endothelial health. Several factors likely contribute to this heterogeneity, including differences in the duration of GP lens wear, the type of lenses

used, the age and health status of participants, and variations in the techniques used to measure endothelial parameters.

Implications for Future Research

The findings from this meta-analysis, combined with evidence from previous studies, suggest that while GP lens wear does not appear to have a significant effect on corneal endothelial parameters, the high heterogeneity and variability across studies prevent definitive conclusions. Future research should focus on standardizing study designs and methodologies, including the use of consistent lens types, uniform measurement techniques, and longer follow-up periods. Large-scale, multicenter studies are needed to better understand the long-term effects of GP lenses on corneal health and to clarify the potential factors contributing to endothelial variability.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while our meta-analysis did not find significant changes in corneal endothelial parameters with GP lens wear, the high level of variability across studies highlights the need for more rigorous and standardized research in this field. Until then, the clinical implications of long-term GP lens wear on corneal endothelial health remain uncertain.

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